

riod at the start of PSP. A statistical analysis of this regression suggests that *O. glaberrima* IG10 had the strongest PPSE (PPSE = 1.46 °C day; $r^2 = 0.91^{**}$). Three other genotypes—CG14, Moroberekan, and WAB450-24-3-2-P18-HB (see table)—also showed significant responses ($P = 0.05$). The regression, however, was not significant in seven genotypes ($P = 0.05$), suggesting that duration to flowering of these varieties was not affected by the range of photoperiod experienced during the trials.

The parameters derived (see table) were inputted into the original (default) and the revised (adapted) INTERCOM crop model. A comparison (on a 1:1 basis) of simulated days to flowering with actual days to flowering is presented in the figure. Results show that days to flowering across genotypes was underestimated by as many as 21 d in the default procedure and by less than 1 d in the adapted procedure. R^2 for the comparison increased from 0.59 in the default

model to 0.94 in the adapted model, which is an index for overall improvement in the prediction. Further evaluation, parameterization, and module development for phenology as affected by photoperiod are required in rice modeling work that involves the use of *O. glaberrima*. Parameterization and validation of the model for key West African rice weeds are also needed.

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Comparisons between observed and simulated duration to flowering (days) of 11 rice varieties at Mbe, Côte d'Ivoire, using the model INTERCOM without (A, default model) and with (B, adapted model) photoperiod effects on duration to flowering.

Virtual rice: simulating the development of plant architecture

T. Watanabe, Department of Information Science and Technology, National Agriculture Research Center, Tsukuba, Ibaraki 3058666, Japan; P.M. Room and J.S. Hanan, Center for Plant Architecture Informatics, Department of Mathematics, University of Queensland, Brisbane, Queensland 4072, Australia

Information on the architecture and morphogenesis of rice plants is important in a range of research fields, such as in the development of ideotypes and direct-seeding techniques and for understanding competition against weeds and compensation for pest dam-

age. Although several simulation models for predicting rice yield exist, there is no detailed model for simulating rice morphogenesis and plant architecture. In this study, the three-dimensional (3D) structure of rice plants was measured and the results were used

to construct a "virtual rice" model that simulates morphogenesis and the development of plant architecture.

The study involved three steps: (1) measurement of the 3D structure at intervals during growth, (2) construction of the

virtual rice model by specifying rules of morphogenesis in the L-system formalism (Lindenmayer 1968), and (3) the use of specialized software that interprets L-system instructions to generate 3D simulations of plant development (Prusinkiewicz and Lindenmayer 1990). Plants of the japonica-type rice "Namaga" were grown in Brisbane, Australia, from September 1997 to February 1998. At the third-leaf stage, seedlings were transplanted singly into 17.5-cm-diam pots filled with loamy soil and fertilizer (10 g N, 11 g P, 8 g K m⁻²). Urea was applied twice during growth: 5 g N m⁻² before panicle initiation and 10 g N m⁻² after panicle initiation. The geometry of the plants was measured using a 3D sonic digitizer interfaced to a special software called FLORADIG[®] (Hanan and Room 2000) that recorded 3D coordinates (x, y, z) labeled according to the types and topological positions of the plant parts. The data were imported into a database and standard query procedures were used to select subsets of data for analysis. The structural development of plant architecture was expressed as mathematical functions and an L-system model was created and tested (Prusinkiewicz and Lindenmayer 1990). The model was interpreted by the Plant and Fractal Generator tool (Mech 1998).

During vegetative development in rice, each apical meristem (A) produces a module that consists of a series of metameters (line 1 in Fig. 1). Each metameter comprises an internode (I), an axillary meristem (B), and a leaf sheath (S) that is connected to a leaf blade (L). At the same time, as the leaf emerges at node n, an axillary bud produces the first leaf of a daughter tiller at node n-

3 on the parent module (line 2 in Fig. 1). The onset of reproductive development occurs when the apical meristem transforms into the initial panicle (P) (line 3 in Fig. 1). Processes such as new meristem production, leaf expansion, tillering, internode elongation, flowering, leaf senescence, and grain maturation were included in the model and related to the developmental index, DVI (Nakagawa and Horie 1995). The

DVI varies continuously from 0 at emergence of the first leaf to 1.0 at the start of panicle initiation, 2.0 at heading, and 3.0 at maturity. As well as numerical output, the model generates realistic images, which can be rotated in 3D at will (Fig. 2).

The virtual rice model could be used to explore the efficiency of light interception of hypothetical plant architecture in the search for improved ideotypes. This

Fig. 1. L-system, production rules, and visualization of corresponding plant growth. A = apical meristem, B = axillary bud, I = internode, S = leaf sheath, L = leaf blade, P = panicle, DVI = developmental index, x = growth of main stem, y = initiation of a tiller, z = panicle initiation.

Fig. 2. Part of a “virtual rice field,” an example of the simulation output.

could be done by changing the values of parameters controlling leaf shape and by using image-processing software to analyze the output. More extensive investigations of the interactions between morphogenesis and the environment, however, will re-

quire virtual rice to be interfaced with an ecophysiological model. This will enable expression of partitioning, calculated by the physiological model, in 3D structure. This is in preparation for analysis of effects on, for example, competition for resources and optimi-

zation of plant population density. Thus, virtual rice has the potential to become a valuable framework for integrating research results from different disciplines and for communicating research output to farmers and others in the form of scientific visualization.

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Source-sink characteristics of japonica/indica hybrid rice

J. Yang, Yangzhou University; S. Peng, IRRI; Z. Wang and Q. Zhu, Yangzhou University, Yangzhou, Jiangsu 225009, China
E-mail: s.peng@cgiar.org

Poor grain filling is the main barrier to using heterosis of japonica/indica hybrid rice (J/I-HR) (Wang et al 1991, Yuan 1990). This study aimed to explain the causes of poor grain filling by investigating the source-sink relations of 36 J/I-HR combinations. Six japonica lines with wide compatibility genes—PC 311, Lunhui 422, Jw-8, Ce-01, 02428, and Ce-03—were used as female parents

and six typical indica lines—Milyang 23, 3037, Zaixiandang-18, IR36, Minghui 63, and Yangdao 4—were used as male parents to make 36 first-generation J/I-HR combinations by the P × Q mode, that is, the females (P) were crossed to the males (Q). An indica hybrid rice combination, Shanyou 63, was used as a control. Seedlings were raised in a greenhouse and transplanted

into the rice field on the Yangzhou University farm, Jiangsu Province, China (32°30’N, 119°25’E) during the 1997 rice-growing season (May–Oct). The experiment was repeated in 1998. Source-sink characteristics were determined by measuring sink size (defined as spikelet number m⁻²), content of nonstructural carbohydrate (NSC) in culms and sheaths, and dry matter accumulation before